

AUTOBIOGRAPHICAL IN PATRIOTIC EDUCATION THE IMPORTANCE OF MEMORY

Mavlanova Saidakhon Umarovna

Sdvmchbu Tashkent branch

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Abstract. This article deals with the allocation of the emotional component and the development of pedagogical and psychological mechanisms of patriotism in the formation of youth spiritual and moral qualities, socially significant functions of autobiographical memory, subject to scientific analysis in the educational process in the context of the patriotic education of youth.

Key words: autobiographical memory, spiritual and moral qualities, patriotic education, personal maturation, national and universal values, pedagogical mechanisms, psychological mechanisms.

Today, a deep and comprehensive focus on the essence of the philosophy of education and upbringing is an important issue than ever, and the survival and perspective of national and universal values depend on it. Formation of spiritual and moral qualities in young people, upbringing of a sense of patriotism is carried out within the framework of a systematic approach, instilling that patriotism is a certain characteristic of a person, plus a virtue, propaganda and it is necessary to effectively organize propaganda work. In this, a clear determination of the trajectory of relations, a responsible approach to the absorption of the quality of patriotism in the minds of young people at all levels of society requires professional competence from each educator.

Also, the separation of the emotional component of patriotism and the development of psychological mechanisms, which occupy an important place in modern society, remains a requirement of the era. In the formation of the attitude towards the motherland, people, national and Universal traditions and culture in young people, it is advisable to instill in the characters of each era the psychological mechanisms of bringing the processes experienced by the heroes of each era into the image of the world of empathetic visions through the use of modern technologies. This process leads to the fact that in the world of consciousness and imagination of each age, the person who made historical heroic patterns is reflected, feels his emotional experiences in himself, and manifests himself in the eyes. In this, the individual feels a sense of national pride and love, expressing a sympathetic attitude towards him nisabatan in a type of realized and unrefined activity. This process testifies to the fact that we expected, that is, a sense of patriotism was formed.

It is no secret that today the Society of man is going through a crisis period associated with youth and their spiritual and moral behavior and upbringing in the spirit of patriotism. Humanity is going through the most complex period of its evolutionary development. The reason is that various forces are using it for their own good in order to divert young people from national and universal ideas and ideologies on the basis of informative prejudices and propaganda, to distance themselves from the belief that willpower should mobilize. In a word,

the number of “passionate and dedicated educators” who are engaged in the upbringing of young people is growing more and more. They are using the influential mechanisms of psychology in this regard, trying to follow the “mass culture” formed on the basis of their false and vain idea by distorting the fundamental changes carried out in their own interests in various spheres of society, including social, political, economic, religious and spiritual, or presenting colorful and charming to a youth audience, marginalizing human values. On the basis of this, the vital orientation of young people goes beyond the trace, views on the issues of Service, duty and responsibility to the state and society are gradually disappearing and becoming more consistent with a sense of patriotism.

In this matter, the researcher Yu.S.Buzikina's scientific and theoretical opinions are significant, and in his view, it is necessary that today's young people live in a constantly changing environment, find an individual identity for self-preservation, and consolidate the factors necessary for its development in the future

His approach from a psychological point of view in the formation of qualities of spiritual maturity and patriotism in young people serves to provide transformative connections with historical memory, opening up new opportunities for understanding social reality and understanding its essence. This process forms the concept of patriotism in the world of imagination that the elements of emergence in the human mind arose on the basis of vital necessity, the realities created by a person himself fell into the sphere of influence, and the transition to the type of activity realized around the ideas of self-preservation, an approach to the territory and ground in which he.

A person's self-awareness is achieved due to a conscious approach to activity, determination of goals and Means, generalization of information about its properties, harmonization of learned theoretical knowledge with practical experience, in today's modern language, autobiographical memory.

Researcher V.V.Nurkova's point of view is that autobiographical memory is a source of subjective relationships of an individual's life, which consists in recording, maintaining, interpreting and carrying out an event and ravines of autobiographical significance, certain situations and circumstances that determine the individuality of the individual.

It should be noted that one of the socially significant functions of autobiographical memory is an emotional image, which can be revered as a factor predicting the systemality of manifestation in cognitive activity, while maintaining the relevance of meaning and essence of events, processes and circumstances important for the individual.

This process, of course, is closely related to the sense of patriotism, which has social significance, embodies emotional meaning and content, the historical progress of the individual, the essence of the personality society, its spiritual pillar.

Each individual can realize himself, reflect on the basis of a sense of patriotism, a sense of belonging to the fate of his family, people, nation and country. In the context of human history, we can observe that self-awareness, the formation and development of a system of national and universal values are associated with the constructive features of autobiographical foundations. In this regard, V.V.Nurkova, in particular, says: "the constructiveness of autobiographical memory determines its practical significance and is carried out in the educational process, in particular in the field of pedagogical - psychological. In patriotic education, autobiographical memory acquires an important Social Psychological

Significance and serves as a kind of “translator” in the perception of material and cultural values by an individual.

An autobiographical memory of a person can, above all, bring to him the opportunity to convey his historical experience to others, and, in addition to the existing experience, to make a promising design of the future. Taking from this point of view, autobiographical memory is a factor that regulates the content of the individual life experience of a person and the mental experiences that occur in him. This factor serves the maturation and rise of the individual by understanding the processes that occur in the life of each person, mastering and strengthening experiences, coordinating the mechanisms of their application in practice.

The maturation and rise of the personality, which is formed on the basis of life experience, ensures the historicity and past at the heart of a patriotic feeling, going to the roots of the ancestor's agitation and life deeds.

Thus, spiritual and educational and patriotic education in young people is also reflected in his personal attitude to environmental autobiography, which is directly related to the glorious path of life, the place where he was born and grew up, traversed by his ancestors. It is also important to purposefully use the experience of identification of the social environment, place of birth and place of birth, National Customs and universal values, as well as other factors in matters of spiritual maturity, educational rise of young people and the effectiveness of their upbringing in the spirit of patriotism. Most importantly, the main task of autobiographical memory is to ensure social harmony, on the basis of which the social activity of young people increases, and their attitude towards national and universal values is formed in the historical and cultural space.

In the context of spiritual and educational and patriotic education of young people, it is advisable to note the issues that must be scientifically analyzed within the educational process:

- first of all, issues of spiritual maturation and absorption of patriotic spirit of youth in modern media communicative practice;
- secondly, the factors of ensuring the Coordination of parallel activities of public organizations with education as promoters of youth spiritual education and the idea of patriotism;
- thirdly, the introduction of a psychological filter of all kinds of advertising and other shows that are not inherent in the national mentality and are inherent in youth education in the media and in all the manifestations that are given through them;
- fourth, the development of a mechanism for active struggle in human consciousness and its healthy Management in the geopolitical space, as well as issues of patriotic phenomenon, national interest and national security, and sovereign immunity;
- fifth, the introduction into all branches of the educational process of innovative methods of reflection in the combination of theoretical and practical activities that national consciousness, national value, spiritual maturity and patriotism are the priority and promising pillar of the development of the state and civil society;
- sixth, the fact that national and universal values are a pedagogical factor in the manifestation of youth in spiritual and educational and patriotic education, and its effective use in cultural and historical conditions;
- seventh, to reveal the pedagogical basis for the fact that national politics, the national economy, national ideology and national spirituality are the ground of patriotism;

- eighth, recommendation to society of patriotic factors and pedagogical mechanisms of its effective use in the context of socio-economic and cultural and political information security;

- ninth, to be a reflection of feelings of patriotism (which, in most cases, is carried out for reporting and pearbogging) in spiritual and educational activities and propaganda and propaganda work aimed at the development and prospects of the state and society;

- thirdly, the development and orientation of patriotic human capital to society, which has demographic problems, issues of gendarmerie and pillars of spiritual, mentally and physically healthy, highly spiritual and stable national value.

In conclusion, it is necessary to purposefully use modern methods of pedagogical technologies in the organization of today's education and upbringing, to model the factors of educating young people in the spirit of spiritual and educational and patriotic in accordance with the above-mentioned scientific-theoretical views, and the emotional modern worldview and the identification of national traditions and universal values is a vital necessity. The approach to this process from a scientific point of view is characterized by National Heroes of the people, persons who have made a high contribution to the state and society with their knowledge and thinking, important historical events serve as a new social motivational ground in the development of personal relations of the youth of society.

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